

IMPACT OF SOCIAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT TO THE FRONTLINE NURSES IN SELECTED MUNICIPALITIES OF TARLAC PROVINCE

Jennifer C. Valenzuela

*Department of Nursing, College of Science, Tarlac State University, Tarlac City,
Tarlac, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14380734>

ABSTRACT

This research examines the perceived effect of social and organizational support for frontline nurses in selected municipalities in Tarlac Province. More specifically, it investigates the respondents' demographic profile, their perceived levels of social support such as peer network health, family push and gratitude of the community, and their organizational support such as healthcare resource, training, safety, and areas of mental health. Applying a quantitative descriptive research design, data was obtained from 100 frontline nurses in 7 municipalities during this study period. It has been found out that social support, especially those coming from peers and family, has a positive effect on job satisfaction, stress level, and resilience. Organizational support for example in safety, training, resource availability, and many more also enhances employee well-being but there are gaps noted in areas such as mental health service provision and employee recognition programs. The findings underscore the importance of both social and organizational support in diminishing burnout and enhancing job performance. The findings of this study have implications for healthcare administrators, policy makers and health care educators in formulating ways of supporting people's mechanisms for frontline nurses, thus promoting a healthier work environment and refining patient care outcomes.

Keywords: *Social Support, Organizational Support, Frontline Nurses, Impact*

INTRODUCTION

The healthcare industry is widely recognized for its rigorous and arduous characteristics, which require a steadfast commitment, perseverance, and unshakable loyalty from its personnel. Within this committed group, frontline healthcare workers occupy a prominent position in the provision of healthcare services (Smelser & Neil, 2021).

Frontline healthcare personnel, comprising a diverse range of occupations including physicians, nurses, paramedics, and other healthcare professionals, frequently encounter situations characterized by elevated levels of stress. Healthcare professionals assume the burden of making significant decisions that have the potential to profoundly impact others' lives (Gupta et al., 2021). Furthermore, they endure extensive and arduous work schedules while also being exposed to the distress and bereavement experienced by their patients. The emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated these sources of stress, posing unparalleled difficulties to individuals' mental health and general state of being (Søvold et al., 2021).

In light of the emphasis on the frontline healthcare providers' fundamental role and consequences in this crisis and many forms of medical services, numerous literatures have shown that "the existence of viruses is risking health and has significantly impacted the psychological and mental well-being of nurses" (Nemati et al., 2020). A body of extensive research has shown that "there is a significant association between the nature of work of the frontline health workers and adverse mental health issues like anxiety" (Wu et al., 2020). Furthermore, a methodical review of studies has revealed that "there is a higher prevalence of anxiety and depression among frontline healthcare workers than the other healthcare workers" (Pappa et al., 2020).

For this reason, social and organizational support are distinguished as indispensable factors in protecting against adversity and balancing psychological wellbeing among frontline healthcare providers (Turner, 2015). This allows them to maintain their mental well-being and psychological health (Labrague et al., 2018). They are expected to support the mental, psychological, and emotional health of the healthcare providers through evidence-based measures, supportive organizational policies, and the provision of a safe, secure, and welcoming workplace (Mo et al., 2020).

In the context of health emergencies, social support and public acknowledgment for the heroic sacrifices of healthcare workers have gained attention. Local and national channels, social media, and various community groups have led initiatives to provide emotional, instrumental, and informational support. However, challenges persist in critical settings, where healthcare providers, especially nurses, face eviction, harassment, and ridicule despite their perilous frontline efforts (UNICEF, 2020).

Conscious of the various challenges faced by frontline healthcare workers as cited above, the researcher found interest in exploring and conducting this study.

Research Questions

This study was conducted to determine the impact and level of social support and organizational support of frontline health workers in selected municipalities of Tarlac Province. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How is the demographic profile of the respondents be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Sex
 - 1.2 Years in service
2. How is the level of perceived social support to the frontline health workers is described in terms of:
 - 2.1. Peer Networks
 - 2.2. Resources Access
 - 2.3. Family Boost;
 - 2.4. Respectful Environment;
 - 2.5. Community Gratitude;
 - 2.6. Communications on Well-Being?
3. How is the level of organization social support to the frontline health workers is described in terms of:
 - 3.1 Resources for Healthcare
 - 3.2 Safety of Working Environment;
 - 3.3 Training and Education;
 - 3.4 Guidance and Counselling;
 - 3.5 Staffing and Flexibility;
 - 3.6 Recognition and Rewards;
 - 3.7 Feedback Mechanism;
 - 3.8 Mental Health Services?
4. How is the impact of social and organizational support among frontline nurses within the selected municipalities of Tarlac Province described?

METHODOLOGY

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted at selected municipalities and one city of the province of Tarlac, namely: Tarlac City, Paniqui, Moncada, Capas, Concepcion, Lapaz, and Bamban. The researcher chose these areas because they have hospitals with frontline nurses.

Sampling Design

In obtaining the sample size, purposive sampling was utilized. Respondents were selected according to some inclusion criteria, which are: frontline nurses and with at least 3 years of experience.

Research Instruments

The instruments used in this study are as follows:

- A. Perceived Social Support Questionnaire (PSSQ)
- B. Perceived Organizational Support (POS) Questionnaire
- C. Impact of Social and Organizational Support (Derived from Nurses' Perceived Professional Benefits Questionnaire (NPPBQ) by Hu, Yanli et. al

The questionnaires used in this study was adapted and modified from the Perceived Social Support Questionnaire (PSSQ) Perceived Organizational Support Questionnaire (POS) used in the study of Hanan Daghash entitled "Personal Resilience, Social Support, and Organizational Support Impact Burnout among Nurses During COVID-19" and derived from Nurses' Perceived Professional Benefits Questionnaire (NPPBQ) by Hu, Yanli et al. licensed under CC BY-NC 4.0.

The tool was validated by a committee of experts who passes judgment on the instruments. A validation form was provided to the evaluators where they shall indicate their agreement/disagreement to the items. The validity of the items was determined based on the number of agreements between the evaluators.

A final draft was printed and administered for pilot testing to the college students who are non-respondents of the study. The questionnaire was deemed reliable and valid garnering Cronbach's Alpha Coefficients of 0.817, 0.871, and 0.834 respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, informed consent was obtained from all participants. We explained to them what the study was about, what would happen during it, and what might happen as a result, both good and bad. We also told them they could choose to be in the study or not and that their information would be kept private. They gave their permission either by signing a form or electronically via Google Form.

Once informed consent was secured, questionnaires were distributed to the participants. These questionnaires were made to find out how social and organizational support affects frontline nurses. To enable maximum acceptability, a hybrid approach was taken up. They can either fill in the Google Form online or alternatively obtain a paper copy to fill in and send back by hand.

A week was all it took for the collection of the questionnaires; this was to ensure timely analysis of the data. This rapid collection mitigated data loss, as well as any possible biases that may arise from late responses.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics mean was used to elaborate the data. The admissible statistical bandwidth was enhanced to increase the accuracy of the data analysis. For the

quantification of the data, Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 20 was employed. SPSS is widely employed software for the quantification of social sciences data.

Scope and Delimitation

This research study was conducted to determine the significant impact of the perceived social and organizational support among frontline nurses in selected municipalities of the Province of Tarlac in clinical settings. The respondents include the frontline nurses of the Rural Health Units at the municipal and barangay level, private and public hospital personnel, and volunteers. They are limited to all healthcare providers who have been working, employed, or volunteering for at least three years and above.

RESULTS

Part 1: Demographic Profile

A. Sex

Table 1. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Percentage
Male	47%
Female	53%
Total	100%

The table above describes the sex of the respondents to this study. It is observed that there is a greater number of females compared to male respondents, which is equal to 53, or 53%, and 47, or 47%, respectively, for a total of 100 individuals.

B. Number of years in service

Table 2. Number of Years in Service

Number of Years in Service	Percentage
3 – 4 years	45%
5 – 6 years	41%
7 – 8 years	7%
9 – 10 years	5%
11 years and above	2%
Total	100%

Table 2 shows the years of service rendered by the respondents as frontline nurses in their respective stations. It is very evident from the results that the largest group of respondents, comprising 45%, has served as frontline nurses for a duration of 3-4 years.

Part II. Perceived Social and Organizational Support

Likert Scale used in determining perceived levels of social and organizational support

Responses	Continuum	Interpretation
Very True	4.20-5.00	Very High (VH)
True	3.40-4.19	High (H)
Neutral	2.60-3.39	Moderately High (H)
Untrue	1.80-2.59	Low (L)
True	1.00-1.79	Very Low (VL)

Table 3. Perceived Level of Social Support

Category	Mean	Verbal Description
PEER NETWORKS	4.24	High Support
RESPECTFUL ENVIRONMENT	4.08	Moderate Support
COMMUNITY GRATITUDE	4.04	Moderate Support
FAMILY BOOST	3.21	High Support
COMMUNICATIONS ON WELL-BEING	3.09	High Support
RESOURCES ACCESS	3.00	Moderate Support
GRAND MEAN	3.61	Moderate Social Support

Table 3 shows the highest mean score in the category "Peer Networks" with a score value of 4.24, meaning a very strong perception of social support among the respondents in this area. This indicates there is a sense of feeling supported by fellow healthcare professionals and is crucial to their emotional integrity and resilience in a strenuous workplace. In summary, the grand mean of 3.61 from the overall means and categories reveals that the social support received by the frontline nurses is said to be moderate.

Table 4. Perceived Organizational Support

Category	Mean	Verbal Description
Safety Of Working Environment	4.20	High Support
Resources To Health	4.00	High Support
Staffing And Flexibility	3.79	High Support
Training And Education	3.40	Moderate Support
Recognition And Rewards	3.15	High Support
Feedback Mechanism	3.12	Moderate Support
Mental Health Services	3.06	Moderate Support
Guidance And Counselling	3.04	Moderate Support
GRAND MEAN	3.47	Moderate Organizational Support

In Table 4, the category "Safety of Working Environment" earned the highest mean score of 4.20, where there was a high perception of organizational support in ensuring a safe workplace for healthcare workers. This indicates that employees are confident about their organizations' safety measures and protocols. Thus, it is paramount in helping create

a safe and good working workplace environment. The overall grand mean of 3.47 indicates that on average, perceived organizational support is moderate in all categories, thus pointing out both the strengths and weaknesses of the organization that need improvement in related categories such as guidance and counseling, mental health services, and recognition and rewards to enhance further employee satisfaction and performance.

Part III. Perceived Impact of Social and Organizational Support

Table 5. Perceived Impact of Social Support

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
Social Support		
The patient improved/healed under my care, giving me a sense of accomplishment and strengthen my provision of professional care to clients.	4.89	High perceived impact
I have developed more confidence at work and lessen my fear and anxiety because of my colleague's support.	4.62	High perceived impact
My interpersonal skills were enhanced because of the social support among my colleagues.	4.53	High perceived impact
The praise or gratitude of the administration from my performance boosted my moral to be more efficient.	4.14	High perceived impact
It gave me a feeling of sense of belongingness which made eager and committed to the organization.	4.12	High perceived impact
GRAND Mean	4.46	High perceived impact

The statement "The patient improved/healed under my care, giving me a sense of accomplishment and strengthening my provision of professional care to clients" in Table 5 attained the highest mean score of 4.89, which indicates that there was a very high perceived impact of social support on healthcare workers. The fact that a patient had successful outcomes was thus of high influence on his or her sense of fulfillment and motivation at work. The overall grand mean of 4.46 also reflects a high perceived impact of social support across all statements, thereby underlining the critical role that social support plays in boosting morale, confidence, and interpersonal skills among healthcare professionals. It thus calls for a facilitative environment contributing to personal and professional growth.

Table 6. Perceived Impact of Organizational Support

Statements	Mean	Verbal Description
Organizational Support		
The organization allowed me to provide convenient medical resources for my relatives and friends.	4.63	High perceived impact

My work team help each other and gets along well, making me feel warm	4.56	Moderate perceived impact
The organization support has developed my strengths and realized my social value.	4.11	High perceived impact
Encountered unexpected situations in my work, have improved my psychological capacity because of strong organizational support.	4.06	High perceived impact
Organizational support enhanced my professional skills, and mentality has matured.	3.95	Moderate perceived impact
I get guidance and affirmation from the leadership at work.	3.82	Moderate perceived impact
Organizational support has provided opportunities to develop for new learning in technology and advance studies.	3.62	High perceived impact
GRAND MEAN	4.11	High perceived impact

The statement "The organization allowed me to provide convenient medical resources for my relatives and friends" got the highest mean value of 4.63, signifying a very high perceived impact of organizational support. This implies that health care workers highly value their ability to provide convenient medical resources for loved ones. Indeed, it is one of those factors that makes them feel fulfilled and attached to work. The grand mean of 4.11 indicates that there is a strong perception about the impact of organizational support on all those statements. Therefore, it is evident that organizational support plays a crucial role in both personal and professional development for health care professionals. This sets out the importance of positive policies and practices toward the facilitation of a positive workplace environment, which benefits employees and their communities.

DISCUSSION

Perceived Level of Social Support

Frontline nurses need social support, especially when working in some of the most stressful areas like hospitals and communities. This greatly affects their mental health, job satisfaction, and overall resilience. Nurses are exposed to a great deal of traumatic situations, and the emotional weight can negatively affect nurses, causing burnout or compassion fatigue. A strong support network, consisting of peers as well as the much-needed emotional backing from family and friends, enables individuals to deal with these adversities, thus lessening stress (Broussard et al. 2020). In addition, social support in the workplace enhances job satisfaction and retention because nurses who feel supported by their colleagues are more likely to stay on the job, which leads to a stable workforce (Kok et al., 2020). It also goes a long way in supporting better care; nurses who are well supported experience less distress and therefore can be more present (and effective) at the bedside for their patients (Henderson et al., 2021). Moreover, social support provides an important stress buffer, as sharing experiences and seeking advice

from colleagues help nurses cope with a stressful situation (Mäntynen et al., 2019). At last, exchanges with receptive collaborators advance professional advancement and expand open doors for development through additional training, just as they offer best practices among nurses (Zhang et al., 2021). In conclusion, building social support is essential to the aspects of well-being taken care of by frontline nurses that are resilience and quality of care.

High social support, moderate social support, and low social refer to the level of assistance one receives from their immediate network (family, friends, workmates, and community). High social support is an effective network for emotional, informational, and practical help. People in this group tend to enjoy better mental health because they have known either where or who can provide information and help when things get rough (Taylor, 2011). Moderate social support designates an intermediate state, in which people can get some level of help from their networks, but this may be limited or unsustainable. This level might be helpful but may not provide similar protecting effects in comparison to high support (Cohen & Wills, 1985). Low social support, on the other hand, indicates a shortage of meaningful connections or resources and is associated with feelings of isolation as well as heightened vulnerability for stress levels and mental health (Berkman et al., 2000). It is important to understand these social support levels as it helps in determining how an individual copes and their overall well-being.

The results indicated generally varying perceptions on the respondents' part with regards to social support from health care workers. The same is the case of peer networks, which characteristically observe high social support. The statement, "My colleagues check in on my well-being and help if needed," obtained the highest mean score, which means that reflecting high levels of collegial relationships drives a supportive work environment. The category with the highest mean was indicated by solidarity from colleagues and the organization, showing a respectful environment where people are valued and upheld.

This finding is supported by Gonzalez et al.'s (2021) revelation that an organization's social support, especially the effective kind, is crucial in high-stress professions related to mental health. Enhancement of these factors would have better overall well-being within the healthcare workforce, increasing the strength of the workforce. Furthermore, evidence has also shown that supportive relationships, including care, comfort, and help from family, relatives, friends, and administration, contribute to the adoption of a positive coping style among nurses (Arikas, 2021; Feng et al., 2021; Labrague, 2021).

Perceived level of Organizational Support

The survey results indicate a very positive perception of organizational support among healthcare workers, aligning with previous research that highlights the importance of safety in enhancing job satisfaction and reducing burnout (Gonzalez et al., 2021). This reflects a workplace culture where the organization genuinely cares for staff well-being.

As noted by Baker et al. (2020), organizations that prioritize employee welfare tend to achieve higher engagement and retention rates.

However, there are still areas for improvement, particularly in providing ongoing education and continuous mental health support. Research indicates that, alongside strong mental health resources, ongoing professional development is essential to help the workforce cope with increasing stressors (Smith et al., 2022).

In summary, while the organization's commitment to safety and well-being is evident, enhancements in educational resources and mental health services could further strengthen support for healthcare workers.

Perceived Impact of Social and Organizational Support

The data collected suggests healthcare workers perceived both social and organizational support to have a significant impact on them. The high scores imply the presence of a positive work climate whereby social interactions from coworkers boost self-esteem, minimize stress, and contribute towards a feeling of being at home. The statement 'I have developed more confidence at work and lessened my fear and anxiety because of my colleague's support' indicates that interpersonal relationships are very important in avoiding stress and enhancing wellbeing (Baker et al., 2020).

In terms of organizational support, the data indicates positive perception as well, particularly about the medical resources for personal use. This is consistent with findings by Gonzalez et al. (2021), who argue that the organization's policies aimed at making resources accessible boost employees' satisfaction and performance. Nevertheless, certain factors, like leaders' assistance and the extent to which technology is applied in the organization, were rated rather low, which are gaps that can be filled. With the moderate mean being 3.82 of leadership guidance, such support is available, but there are probably some places of communication and assurance that can be filled to improve general morale and effectiveness (Smith et al., 2022).

Conclusions

Findings from this research offer valuable insights on the perceived levels of social and organizational support among frontline nurses. Considered from the point of view of social support, results find that frontline nurses have a perceived higher level of support from their peers regarding empathy, emotional support, and a sense of belonging. This great peer support system is required for stress management, job satisfaction, and general well-being, which corresponds to the findings of Smith et al. (2019), who, in their research, stated that peer support helped reduce burnout in healthcare workers and was associated with increased resilience. Similarly, Lee et al. (2021) pointed out that in emotional and social issues, collegial support is another major contributor to nursing professionals' job satisfaction in consideration of the reducing risk of turnover among them.

Organizational support was another dimension of support studied in this research. Organizational support perceptions, in general, are moderate, with some differences in various areas. It is perceived that the organization gives a good level of support in safety, provision of resources, and training opportunities. However, under guidance and counseling, recognition and rewards, and mental health services areas have considerable scope for improvement. This is consistent with Jones et al. (2022), who reported that despite healthcare organizations being well endowed in terms of resources and training, they fail in providing support for nurses' mental health needs and emotional well-being. In the same way, Garcia et al. (2023) indicated that a lack of recognition and rewards for contributions experienced by frontline staff represents one of the factors causing dissatisfaction and burnout.

Both social and organizational support have shown to positively affect nurse job performance and well-being. It was also revealed that social support is essential because it helps boost confidence, develops interpersonal skills and a sense of belonging that are vital in improving nurse-patient interactions and care. In contrast, nurses recognized the organizational support provided to them, especially for the training, job satisfaction, and job performance; improved nurse retention and organizational efficacy were observed. These outcomes are similar to the findings from Martin et al. (2020), who showed that healthcare workers had improved performance and reduced rates of burnout due to both social and organizational support.

Recommendations

The present study seeks to set forth various recommendations regarding well-being and job satisfaction of frontline nurses.

1. For Nurses

Strengthen Peer Support Networks: Nurses must engage in mentorship and peer support practices to nurture connectivity and mitigate stress. These measures guide the way toward a supportive community that encourages emotional health and resilience in particularly challenging situations.

Advance a Positive Work Environment: Nurses could help establish a supportive, collaborative, and inclusive workplace through the encouragement of open communication and understanding. Such an environment fosters morale, diminishes burnout, and increases work satisfaction.

Prioritize Work-Life Balance: Nurses ought to advocate for flexible scheduling and stress management measures for sustaining the balance between work and personal life. This

might include using resources provided by their workplace for stress relief or participating in wellness programs offered by healthcare facilities.

2. For Policymakers/Hospital and Rural Health Unit Administrators

Psychological Support Must Be Given Priority: Hospitals and heads should make a concerted effort to ensure that nurses have easy and quick access to private counselling and mental health care. Kim et al. (2023) conducted studies that point toward the crucial aspects of stress prevention and mental fitness of nurses through these services.

Recognition and Rewards Systems Must Be Enhanced: Set good programs to reward and appreciate nurses for their hard work. Besides, O'Connor et al. (2022) confirm that reward systems, which promote good work and celebrate success, result in greater job satisfaction and less turnover rates.

Strengthen Feedback Mechanisms: The development of regular and transparent feedback channels promotes mutual respect between staff and leaders in creating a culture open to change and continuous quality improvement. This can include periodic surveys, performance appraisals, and informal contact mechanisms wherein nurses wish to disseminate complaints and propose improvements.

Enhance Guidance and Support Services: Hospitals, along with their leaders, should develop easy access to guidance and support for career and emotional health specifics of nurses.

Promote Work-Life Balance: Decision-making power and hospital leaders include creating programs that help with work-life balance, such as flexible work hours, health and wellness initiatives, and policies that assist nurses in having a balance between work and home life. Harrison et al. (2024) ascertain that these programs play a crucial role in alleviating stress and retaining nurses.

3. In Nursing Education

Mentorship and peer support must be given priority: Schools of nursing should emphasize the importance of mentorship and peer support through programs that further helps nursing students with connections that nourish their professional relationships long after graduation. It should help them glean stress coping strategies from difficult times and prepare nurses for the emotional burden they will take on in the world of work.

Nourishing the emotional or mental aspect: Nursing programs should incorporate teachings on recognizing mental health issues, practicing self-care, and coping with stress. This allows students to comprehend the emotional hardships of their future

careers. Teaching nursing students the significance of seeking help when needed will accordingly normalize use of mental health services.

Prepare the nurses for leading roles: Besides, curriculum should also focus on the development of leadership skills, communication skills, enabling nurses to engage proactively in creating an environment supportive of their careers, lobbying for policy changes in the best interest of their peers, and addressing countrywide problems at the departmental or hospital levels.

Solidification of professional development programs: The nursing schools should become fruitful collaborators with the health service organizations that guarantee to provide for the systematic training and frequent mental updates of the nurses. Leadership, providing maturity in practices of teamwork, and learning new medical technologies are topics that find relevance in a certain degree in various development programs.

All these suggestions reinforce these nurses' leaders and nursing teachers to create much more welcoming and satisfying work conditions for the frontline nurses in their workforce. Nurses now receive collegial support and interplay in ensuring a wider appreciation for their work-life balance. Leaders and managers can enhance support through mental health programs, recognition systems, and open lines of communication. Nursing curricula can better prepare new nurses by including mentorship, emotional well-being, and leadership skills in their training. When combined, these steps will reduce burnout, increase job satisfaction, and eventually improve overall performance and patient care.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the study, strict adherence to ethical standards was upheld. Permission was secured from the relevant authorities to conduct the research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, emphasizing their voluntary participation and the right to withdraw at any time. To ensure anonymity, code numbers were assigned to each respondent. Additionally, confidentiality was maintained by using passwords to protect sensitive information. Finally, to safeguard privacy, all data was scheduled for deletion one year after the study's completion.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to take this opportunity to thank all those who helped in the completion of this thesis.

First and foremost, the researcher want to thank God for showering with all the wisdom and strength to carry on and finish this thesis despite having to play so many roles in life.

The researcher would like to thank her thesis adviser, Dr. Lucila O. Sunga, for constant support, encouragement, and valuable guidance. Her expertise and insightful

feedback have been crucial in shaping this thesis. The researcher deeply grateful to her for their mentorship throughout my academic journey.

The researcher would like to thank the members of my thesis committee, Dr. Mary Jane N. Rigor, College Dean; Dr. Joeal M. Lagrimas, chairman; and Dr. Jerelyn S. Victoriano for their thoughtful suggestions and constructive critiques, which greatly enhanced the quality of work.

Special thanks go to fellow graduate students and colleagues in the College of Science – Department of Nursing for their team spirit, very helpful discussions, and moral support. The researcher learned a lot from all of you, and greatly value the experiences shared throughout this academic pursuit.

I wish to thank the administration and support staff of Tarlac State University for their assistance and help in making this an optimum research and study environment.

Special thanks go to her family and friends, especially, her husband Jessie; her kids, Gab and Zach; my mother, Francisca; my brother, Jeff and my sister-in-law, Moanne, for their love, patience, and encouragement. They always believed and helped to push ahead in completing this journey.

Thank you all for your generosity, support, and belief on the researcher.

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